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nasibahon0050@mail.ru**LABORATORY RESEARCH PREGNANT WOMEN WITH HERPETIC STOMATITIS** <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7632389>**ABSTRACT**

Pregnant women with CGP and herpetic stomatitis were examined at various gestation periods. A low level of IL-10 in the oral fluid was revealed in pregnant women with herpetic stomatitis, more pronounced in the II trimester of the gestational period. According to Sukhikh G.T., Vanko L.V. (2005) and Prokhodnaya V.A. successful gestation. It should be noted that three main immunological mechanisms of fetal rejection are indicated in the literature: exposure to symmetrical cytotoxic antibodies, Th1-dependent immune response pathway, Th2-mediated cellular responses, and embryo-destructive effects of natural killers (NK) (Sidelnikova V.M., 2007).

Keywords: pregnancy, herpetic stomatitis, IL-10, oral fluid, blood, oral mucosa, kpu, spitn indices.

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nasibahon0050@mail.ru**ЛАБОРАТОРНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ У БЕРЕМЕННЫХ ЖЕНЩИН С
ГЕРПЕТИЧЕСКИМ СТОМАТИТОМ****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Обследованы беременные женщины с ХГП и герпетическим стоматитом в различные сроки гестации. Выявлено низкий уровень ИЛ-10 в ротовой жидкости у беременных герпетическим стоматитом, более выраженной во II-триместре гестационного периода. По мнению Сухих Г.Т., Ванько Л.В.(2005) и Проходная В.А и соав.(2017), физиологически протекающая беременность характеризуется отсутствием выраженного материнского клеточно-опосредованного иммунитета против чужеродных (отцовских) антигенов плода, что является условием успешного вынашивания плода. Необходимо отметить, что в литературных источниках указаны три основные иммунологические механизмы отторжения плода:

воздействие симметричных цитотоксических антител, Th1-зависимый путь иммунного ответа, Th2-опосредованные клеточные реакции и эмбриодеструктивное влияние натуральных киллеров (NK) (Сидельникова В.М., 2007).

Ключевые слова: беременность, герпетический стоматит, ИЛ-10, ротовая жидкость, кровь, слизистая оболочка полости рта, индексы КПУ, CPITN.

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HERPETİK STOMATIT BO'LGAN HOMILADOR AYOLLARDA LABORATORIYA TEKSHIRUVI

ANNOTATSIYA

CGP va herpetik stomatit bilan og'rigan homilador ayollar turli homiladorlik davrlarida tekshirildi. Og'iz suyuqligida IL-10 ning past darajasi gerpetik stomatit bilan og'rigan homilador ayollarda aniqlangan, bu homiladorlik davrining II trimestrida aniqroq. Sukhikh G.T., Vanko L.V. (2005) va Proxodnaya V.A.ga ko'ra muvaffaqiyatli homiladorlik. Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, adabiyotda homilani rad etishning uchta asosiy immunologik mexanizmi ko'rsatilgan: simmetrik sitotoksik antikorlarning ta'siri, immun javobning Th1 ga bog'liq yo'li, Th2 vositachiligidagi hujayrali reaksiyalar va tabiiy qotillarning embrionni buzuvchi ta'siri. (NK) (Sidelnikova V.M., 2007).

Kalit so'zlar: homiladorlik, gerpetik stomatit, IL-10, og'iz suyuqligi, qon, og'iz bo'shlig'i shilliq qavati, KPU, CPITN indekslari.

Introduction

According to Sukhikh G.T., Vanko L.V. (2005) and Proxodnaya V.A. successful gestation. It should be noted that three main immunological mechanisms of fetal rejection are indicated in the literature: the effect of symmetrical cytotoxic antibodies, the Th1-dependent pathway of the immune response, Th2-mediated cellular reactions, and the embryo-destructive effect of natural killers (NK) (Sidelnikova V.M., 2007).

According to the majority of authors [Gazieva I.A. et al., 2010; Calleja-Agius J., Muttukrishna S., Jauniaux E., 2012], the immunological mechanisms of preserving pregnancy and protecting the embryo consist in the formation of asymmetric blocking antibodies that do not have a high affinity for fetal antigens and do not cause activation of cytotoxic reactions. At the same time, according to Posisev, L.V. and Sotnikov N.Yu. [2007], the detection of an increased content of Th1 cytokines does not always correlate with an unfavorable course and outcome of pregnancy, and, conversely, in obstetric pathology, a high level of Th2-profile cytokines can be noted.

In our opinion, these immunological changes are also closely related to the hormonal status, where endogenous progesterone has immunosuppressive properties, suppressing the production of Th1-cytokines and, therefore, shifting the Th1/Th2 balance towards the predominance of Th2 [Shirshov S.V., 2005].

Purpose of the study: The aim of this study was to study the level of IL-10 in the oral fluid and blood in pregnant women with herpetic stomatitis.

Material and research methods: 76 pregnant women who were observed on the basis of TGSI were examined. Of the total number of pregnant women examined (the main group), 36 pregnant women were diagnosed with mild chronic generalized periodontitis, 40 pregnant women were diagnosed with herpetic stomatitis. This group of pregnant women with herpetic stomatitis

consisted of patients with frequently recurrent HSV infection with viruses of the Herpesviridae family and the number of exacerbations from 4 to 6 per year. The diagnosis of herpetic stomatitis infection in the examined pregnant women was established on the basis of clinical data: patient complaints, history taking.

To detect HSV, a number of molecular biological methods are also currently used, such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and molecular DNA hybridization reaction, which make it possible to detect the presence of viral nucleic acid in the test material. The examined women were involved in observation at various gestational ages. The comparison group (18 women) consisted of women with uncomplicated pregnancy (22-32 weeks). The control group consisted of 14 healthy women of reproductive age. The average age of the examined persons was from 18 to 26 years. Dental status was examined using dental indices in the first, second and third trimesters of pregnancy.

In this case, the KPU caries index, the Green-Vermillion oral hygiene index (OHI-S), the PMA papillary-marginal-alveolar index and the CPITN periodontal index were used. In all pregnant women in all periods of gestation (I-trimester (8-12 weeks), II-trimester (16-24 weeks) and III-trimester (27-38 weeks) of the gestational period, oral fluid was collected using the methods of N. A. Terekhina, Yu.A. Petrovich et al.(2010) To study the content of cytokines, we used oral fluid collected on an empty stomach, in the morning, without stimulation, as well as venous blood of patients taken from 8 to 10 am in plastic tubes BD Vacutainer (BD Bioscience).

Research results: Known. That the fetoplacental tissues of pregnant women spontaneously secrete cytokines that inhibit the cellular immune response and promote the humoral response: interleukins (IL)-10. Trophoblast cells, also at all stages of pregnancy, actively produce IL-10, the biological activity of which is manifested by the suppression of the cellular specific immune response. Thus, the development of pregnancy is accompanied by a decrease in the functional activity of natural killers of the mother's body, which contributes to the preservation of the fetus.

Inhibition of natural killers and a decrease in the production of γ -interferon contributes to the prevalence of differentiation of T-helpers Th2, producing interleukins 4, 6, 10, 13, etc., which suppress the cell-mediated immune response. Herpes simplex virus infection is often accompanied by significant disturbances in the regulation of the immune response by the interleukin (IL) system. These disorders can be associated with both a decrease in interleukin production and a change in the response of target cells to synthesized ILs.

Our clinical and laboratory studies of pregnant women at various times of the gestational period showed the presence of herpes simplex on the lips and oral mucosa. One of the objectives of our study was to assess the hygienic state of the oral cavity and determine the intensity and prevalence of inflammatory periodontal diseases and their impact on the intensity, prevalence, course and severity of herpetic stomatitis.

As studies have shown, the main group of pregnant women were characterized by high rates of the OHI-S hygiene index from 3.3 ± 0.12 to 2.9 ± 0.11 , where the bleeding index reached 3 and 4 degrees, the PMA index reached 68% or more, the value of the KPI index ranged from 3 to 3.6 points, the KPI index was characterized by the predominance of the constant "K". An index assessment of the dental status of patients with herpetic stomatitis testified to the progression of this pathology during pregnancy with an increase in the severity of the disease, a deterioration in the hygienic state of the oral cavity, and an increase in indices reflecting the condition of the gums and periodontal hard tissues.

Analysis of the obtained research results presented in Table 1

Table 1

The content of interleukin-10 (IL-10) in the oral fluid and blood serum of pregnant women with mild CGP

Index	Healthy faces n=14	Healthy pregnant women n=18	Pregnant women with CHRONIC GENERALIZED PERIODONTITIS n=36		
			I trimester n=12	II I trimester n=12	III I trimester n=12

Oral fluid pg/ml	10,45±0,86	11,36±0,94	12,14±1,17	10,05±2,13	10,87±2,79
Serum pg/ml	6,21±0,53	9,93±0,78*	8.03±0,66*	7,14±0,61	7.81±0,59*

Note: * - reliability of differences $P < 0.05$ relative to the indicators of the comparison groups as well as in pregnant women with CGP at various times of the gestational period. In our opinion, high levels of IL-10 in the blood serum are aimed at maintaining pregnancy and increasing not only humoral immunity, but also hormonal status, which is associated with the fetoplacental complex.

The dynamics of the content of IL-10 in the oral fluid had its own characteristic features. In particular, there was a decrease in the level of IL-10 in the 1st trimester of pregnancy by a factor of 2.74 in the 2nd trimester and by 54% in the 3rd trimester relative to healthy individuals. When comparing the obtained results with the indicators of healthy pregnant women, there was a decrease in the level of IL-10 on average: in the 1st trimester by 54%, in the 2nd trimester - by 3.4 times and in the 3rd trimester - 58%.

Discussion of the results

Currently, herpes virus infection in women and its impact on the course of pregnancy and childbirth attracts the attention of many researchers. One of the little studied aspects of the pathogenesis of herpes infection is the state of the cytokine system, which is determined by the expression of immune response genes. During pregnancy, aggravated with herpetic stomatitis, changes in the cytokine profile, as shown by our data, are more pronounced.

As a result of the study, we revealed an extremely low content of IL-10 in the oral fluid of pregnant women with herpetic stomatitis in the 2nd trimester of the gestational period. One of the main functions of IL-10 is the inhibition of cellular immunity and stimulation of steroidogenesis (progesterone, hCG), as well as the production of blocking antibodies. In addition, IL-10 plays an important role in the differentiation of Th-0 into the Th-2 phenotype, has an inhibitory effect on the production of prostaglandins and cytokines by macrophages, and also enhances the expression of HLA-G molecules on trophoblast cells, which are necessary for successful embryo implantation and maintenance activity of Th-2 cells. In the studies of Wegmann T.G., Lin H., Guilbert L. (1993)4 Sidelnikova V.M., (2005), it has been shown that inhibition of IL-10 production in the early stages causes abortion.

Conclusions. Pregnancy complicated by herpetic stomatitis is accompanied by a decrease in the level of IL-10 in the oral fluid, more pronounced in the II trimester of the gestational period

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